

**A Novel Theory of Tripartate Conjugate
and its Application to Synthesise Soluble
Macromolecular Conjugates**

A. BHATTACHARYYA

Division of Biochemical Engineering,
Indian Institute of Chemical Biology,
4 Raja S. C. Mullick Road, Calcutta-700 032

*Manuscript received 28 December 1989,
revised 7 November 1990, accepted 7 March 1991*

It is often necessary to conjugate a small organic molecule with a macromolecule like protein for various purposes like affinity design, antibody production, drug delivery, targeting etc.¹. If the organic molecule is insoluble in water, as it happens to be in many cases, it becomes extremely difficult to carry out the conjugation reaction, and even in case the reaction can be carried out, the product conjugate often becomes insoluble, and hence unusable for biological experiments.

To surmount these dual difficulties, herein has been designed a tripartate conjugate: ligand-bridge-protein, in which the insoluble organic compound (ligand) is coupled to the macromolecule (protein) via a very hydrophilic water-soluble molecule (bridge). To serve the chemical and biological purpose most satisfactorily, an ideal bridge compound must satisfy the following conditions: (i) It must have a number of functional groups which can be utilised in linking it to the organic molecule on one side and to the macromolecule on the other, but still having left with some more hydrophilic groups to impart solubility to the overall conjugate, (ii) it must be covalently linked to the ligand and protein, (iii) it must release the ligand easily under hydrolytic conditions, as and when necessary (as in controlled release and delivery of drugs) and (iv) it must act as an arm only and not change the biological property of the ligand. Also, it is desirable that the bridge should be cheap and easily available. It has been found that citric acid fulfils all the criteria of the ideal bridge.

Scheme 1

Experimental

Citric acid (G.R., Sarabhai M.), pyrimethamine, primaquine, bovine serum albumin (BSA) and 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide (EDC) (all Sigma) and rifamycin B (Ciba-Geigy) were used. Organic solvents were of A.R. quality.

General procedure: The methodology involves two-step reaction sequence (Scheme 1): (i) synthesis of citrate derivative (3) (an amide or ester) of the ligand (1; L-XH) in an organic solvent like dimethylformamide (DMF) or dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) in presence of EDC as catalyst and (ii) conjugation of 3 with the macromolecule in water or water-organic solvent mixture in presence of catalyst. This general methodology can be illustrated taking the typical case of pyrimethamine as illustrated below.

Synthesis of pyrimethamine-citrate: To pyrimethamine (5; 2 mmol, 498 mg) dissolved in DMSO (15 ml), first citric acid (2; 2 mmol, 420 mg) and then EDC (7 mmol) were slowly added with stirring. The colour gradually changed from golden yellow to deep wine-red within 5 min. The clear reaction mixture was stirred for 1.5 h at room temperature and lyophilised to obtain a brown semisolid whose tlc was noted (silica gel, $\text{CHCl}_3 - \text{CH}_3\text{OH} = 1:1$ (v/v), uv light to detect the bands).

Conjugation of pyrimethamine-citrate (Pm-Ct) with BSA: To Pm-Ct (0.5 mmol) dissolved in a mixture of water (15 ml) and DMF (5 ml), BSA (350 mg) was added slowly with stirring and EDC (1.5 g) with finally added over a period of 1 min. The deep wine-red clear solution (pH 5.5) was stirred for 2 h at room temperature, then dialysed against distilled water (4×1 L; 48 h) at 4° and lyophilised. The product can also be stored in solution in frozen condition. Estimation of molar ratio of pyrimethamine: BSA was carried out by biuret method for protein and calculating pyrimethamine from standard curve of Pm-Ct, plotted absorbance versus concentration.

Citrate derivatives of rifamycin B (Rn) (6) and primaquine free base (Pq) (7): The citrate derivatives were prepared from citric acid and the compound in equimolecular amounts in presence of 5 times (molar ratio) of EDC in DMF as solvent following the procedure given above. Tlc was carried out on silica gel and developed by $\text{MeOH} - \text{CHCl}_3$ (4:1, v/v) in case of rifamycin citrate and by $\text{MeOH} - \text{CHCl}_3$ (1:1) in case of primaquine derivative. The products were conjugated with BSA in aqueous medium as above.

Results and Discussion

All the three compounds have very low solubility in water: 5 is insoluble 6 has solubility of 0.027% and the primaquine free base (7) is sparingly soluble. All these were successfully converted to soluble citrate derivatives.

Since **5** has two amino groups attached to the aromatic ring, it may be expected to produce 2-citrate and 4-citrate, with 2-citrate predominating because of the steric factor. Tlc pattern was in accordance, showing only traces of unreacted **5** ($R_f=0.76$) and two bands for products with $R_f=0.69$ and 0.45 , the later being the major product. Some traces of product was found near the solvent front probably due to the formation of dicitrate. The ir spectrum was in agreement with the functional groups. In uv spectrum the compound **5** absorbs strongly around 300 nm with λ_{max} at 315 and 276 nm, while the product citrate shows a shoulder around 346 nm. This shoulder has been used in the present work as representative for detection and estimation of the product.

Similarly, the citrates of **6** and **7** were detected and estimated from uv absorption. The absorption maxima of **7** and its citrate were the same (352 nm). In case of **7**, the product ($R_f=0.87$) was well-separated from **7** ($R_f=0.43$) and the yield was ca 45%. In case of **6**, however, there was only traces of unreacted **6** ($R_f=0.91$) with the overlapping products coming at $R_f=0.59$ and only traces of another product could be observed in between. It is interesting to note that there was no shift of λ_{max} after conversion of **6** to its citrate, thus indicating phenolic OH groups remaining unperturbed, and that the esterification has probably occurred through C_{21}/C_{23} hydroxyl groups. It may be noted here that this feature of esterification at 21/23 positions may have important implications, as for example, it may be necessary to leave the aromatic ring undisturbed for raising specific antibodies².

All the tripartate conjugates ligand-citrate-protein have been found to have reasonably good molar ratio of ligand : protein, for example, pyrimethamine-citrate-BSA conjugate showed pyrimethamine : protein molar ratio of 15 : 1. It may be mentioned here that this feature is extremely important from biochemical point of view³, because it is always desirable to have high proportion of the ligand in antibody raising, drug delivery or targeting.

The methodology developed is very simple, straightforward and fast, involving only two steps which can easily be carried out in any biochemical laboratory. It should find wide applications in biochemical problems where insolubility of the organic compound creates serious bottleneck in designing any experiment. The only condition that has to be satisfied is that the insoluble organic compound must have a OH or NH₂ group.

Acknowledgement

The author is sincerely grateful to Dr. S. K. Basu, Director, I.M.T., Chandigarh, for facilities.

References

1. "Macromolecules as Drugs and as Carriers for Biologically Active Materials", eds. D. A. TIRRELL, L. G. DONARUMA and A. B. TURK, New York

- Academy of Sciences, New York, 1985, p. 1; P D SHARMA, *J. Sci. Ind Res*, 1986, **45**, 534; K J WIDDER and R. GREEN, *Methods Enzymol (A)*, 1985, **112**, 259.
- 2 A. BHATTACHARYYA, *Curr. Sci.* 1990, **59**, 382.